

2,4-Diethoxy-5-Alkylbenzenealkanamine Hydrochlorides as Possible Amoebicides

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Synthesis of some 2,4-diethoxy-5-alkylbenzenealkanamines starting from the corresponding acetophenones and benzaldehydes has been described. The compounds have been tested *in vitro* for amoebicidal activity against *E. histolytica*.

RETENTION of dimethoxy moiety on phenyl ring has been regarded as essential for the maintenance of amoebicidal activity in benzenealkanamines^{1,2}. We have, however, observed that mixed ethoxy, methoxy and isomeric compounds show enhanced activity^{3,4} than the corresponding dimethoxy analogues^{5,6}. In the present paper we report the synthesis and the *in vitro* amoebicidal activity of some 2,4-diethoxy-5-alkylbenzenealkanamine hydrochlorides.

2,4-Diethoxy-5-alkylacetophenones (I) have been converted into 2,4-diethoxy-5-alkyl- α -methylbenzenemethanamines (III) via their oximes (II). 2,4-Diethoxy-5-alkylbenzaldehydes (IV) have been converted into 2,4-diethoxy-5-alkylbenzeneethanamines (VI) via the corresponding nitrostyrenes (V) and into 2,4-diethoxy-5-alkylbenzenepropanamines (X) via the corresponding cinnamic acids (VII), benzenepropionic acids (VIII) and benzenepropanamides (IX). The amines have been isolated as hydrochlorides and tested *in vitro* for amoebicidal activity.

Amoebicidal activity :

Solutions of the amine hydrochlorides in sterile distilled water after Seitz filtration were tested *in vitro* for minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) against axenically grown *E. histolytica* by the cavity

slide method⁷. The results are shown in Table I along with MIC values for the corresponding dimethoxy and mixed ethoxy methoxy amine hydrochlorides.

From a comparison of MIC values it is obvious that in addition to the increase in activity with increasing length of the alkyl chain, the effect of changing methoxy moiety by ethoxy moiety is much more pronounced. For the same alkyl chain the activity shows a progressive increase with progressive introduction of the ethoxy moiety.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. ¹H NMR was recorded with TMS as internal standard and chemical shifts are reported in δ (ppm) units.

2,4-Diethoxy-5-alkyl- α -methylbenzenemethanamines (III) : 2,4-Diethoxy-5-alkylacetophenones, prepared by the usual Nencki reaction of 4-alkylresorcinols, were ethylated with diethylsulphate by K_2CO_3 /acetone method. The ketones were crystallized from ethyl acetate-pet. ether as solids, m.p. Ia 87°, Ib 61-2°, Ic 55-6°, and were characterised by elemental

TABLE I—2,4-DIETHOXY-5-ALKYLBENZENEALKANAMINE HYDROCHLORIDES AND THEIR *in vitro* AMOEBICIDAL ACTIVITY

Compound	R	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)			Amoebicidal activity (µg/ml)		
				C	H	N	Test compound	Corresponding 2,4-dimethoxy analogues	Corresponding mixed ethoxy methoxy analogues
2,4-Diethoxy-5-alkyl-α-methylbenzenemethanamine hydrochlorides									
IIIa	Et	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₂ NCl	228	61.95 (61.42)	8.86 (8.77)	5.10 (5.12)	N.A.*	1000	500
IIIb	n-Pr	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₂ NCl	214	62.56 (62.61)	9.98 (9.04)	4.63 (4.87)	N.A.*	1000	500
IIIc	n-Bu	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₂ NCl	190	63.80 (63.90)	9.46 (9.92)	4.76 (4.66)	N.A.*	1000	500
2,4-Diethoxy-5-alkylbenzeneethanamine hydrochlorides									
VIa	Me	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ NCl	227	60.10 (60.19)	8.46 (8.49)	5.32 (5.39)	250	1000	—
VIb	Et	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ O ₂ NCl	280	61.46 (61.42)	8.90 (8.77)	5.16 (5.12)	125	1000	250
VIc	n-Pr	C ₁₅ H ₂₃ O ₂ NCl	198	62.54 (62.61)	8.99 (9.04)	4.90 (4.87)	62.5	1000	125
VI d	n-Bu	C ₁₆ H ₂₅ O ₂ NCl	175-6	63.82 (63.90)	9.35 (9.92)	4.69 (4.66)	62.5	250	62.5
2,4-Diethoxy-5-alkylbenzenepropanamine hydrochlorides									
Xa	Me	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₂ NCl	155	61.41 (61.42)	8.72 (8.77)	5.08 (5.12)	250	1000	—
Xb	Bt	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₂ NCl	121-22	62.45 (62.61)	9.16 (9.04)	4.89 (4.87)	250	500	500
Xc	n-Fr	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₂ NCl	114-15	63.98 (63.90)	9.21 (9.92)	4.56 (4.66)	62.5	250	62.5

* Non-active at 1000 µg/ml.

analysis and spectral data. IR ν_{\max}^{KBr} cm⁻¹: 1660 (>C=O stretch). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ 1.0-1.2 (t, -CH₃), 1.50 (t, -OCH₂-CH₃ and m, buried Ar-CH₂-CH₂-CH₂-), 2.56 (s, -COCH₃ and t, buried Ar-CH₂), 4.13 (q, -OCH₂-), 6.33 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.56 (1H, s, Ar-H).

I were converted into the corresponding oximes with NH₂OHHCl and sodium acetate by the usual procedure, crystallized from aq. alcohol as white needles, m.p. IIa 154-55°, IIb 138-39°, IIc 128-29°. These were also characterised by elemental analysis and spectral data.

II were reduced by refluxing with zinc dust, ammonium acetate, liquor ammonia and alcohol⁸. The amines (III) were isolated as hydrochlorides by passing dry HCl through their dry ethereal solutions. The amine hydrochlorides were crystallized from methanol-ethyl acetate as white shining solids. IR ν_{\max}^{KBr} cm⁻¹: 3020-2860 (N-H stretch), 1580 and 1505 (N-H bend). ¹H NMR (TFA): δ 1.0-1.66 (m, -CH₃ and saturated -CH₂-), 2.60 (2H, t, Ar-CH₂-), 4.20 (4H, q, -OCH₂-), 6.70 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.1 (1H, s, Ar-H).

2,4-Diethoxy-5-alkylbenzeneethanamines (VI): 2, 4-Diethoxy-5-alkylbenzaldehydes (IV) were prepared by formylation of 2,4-diethoxyalkylbenzenes by Vilsmeier reaction. These were crystallized from light petroleum as white flaky solids, m.p. IVa 100-1°, IVb 72-3° (lit⁹ m.p. 72-3°), IVc 78-9° (lit⁹ m.p.

79-80°), IVd 52-3°, and were characterised by analytical and spectral data. IR ν_{\max}^{KBr} cm⁻¹: 2880 and 2760 (C-H stretch of -CHO), 1665 (>C=O stretch). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ 1.0-1.2 (t, CH₃), 1.50 (t, -OCH₂-CH₃ and m, buried, Ar-CH₂-CH₂-CH₂-), 2.56 (t, Ar-CH₂-), 4.13 (4H, q, -OCH₂-), 6.30 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.56 (1H, s, Ar-H), 10.0 (-CH=O).

IV were converted into corresponding 2,4-diethoxy-5-alkyl-β-nitrostyrenes (V) by condensation with nitromethane in presence of ammonium acetate and glacial acetic acid. These were crystallized from methanol as yellow plates, m.p. Va 135-36° (lit¹⁰ m.p. 115-17°), Vb 108° (lit⁸ m.p. 108-9°), Vc 97-8° (lit⁹ m.p. 98-9°), Vd 88-9°. These were also characterised by analytical and spectral data. ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ 6.33 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.1 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.6 (1H, d, J=14.0 Hz, -CH=CH-NO₂), 7.96 (1H, d, J=14.0 Hz, -CH=CH-NO₂).

V were reduced with LAH in anhydrous ether and the amines (VI) were isolated as hydrochlorides by passing dry HCl through their ethereal solutions. The amine hydrochlorides were crystallized from methanol-ethylacetate as white shining flaky solids.

IR ν_{\max}^{KBr} cm⁻¹: 3030-2840 (b, N-H stretch), 1580 and 1510 (N-H bend). ¹H NMR (TFA): δ 1.0-1.2 (t, -CH₃), 1.50 (t, -OCH₂-CH₃ and m, buried, Ar-CH₂-CH₂-CH₂-), 2.2 (3H, Ar-CH₃), 2.60 (2H, t, Ar-CH₂-), 3.13 (2H, t, Ar-CH₂-CH₂-

NH_2), 3.50 (2H, m, $\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{NH}_2$), 4.20 (4H, q, $-\text{OCH}_2-$), 6.76 (1H, s, $\text{Ar}-\text{H}$), 7.06 (1H, s, $\text{Ar}-\text{H}$).

2,4-Diethoxy-5-alkylbenzenepropanamines (X) : 2,4-Diethoxy-5-alkylbenzaldehydes (VI) were condensed with malonic acid in pyridine as solvent and piperidine as catalyst and the corresponding cinnamic acids (VII) were crystallized from aq. alcohol as light yellow solids, m.p. VIIa 146°, VIIb 155-56°, VIIc 140°. These were characterised by analytical and spectral data. IR $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ cm^{-1} : 1680 (>C=O stretch).

VII were reduced with 3% Na/Hg and the corresponding benzenepropanoic acids (VIII) were crystallized from aq. alcohol as white solids, m.p.

VIIIa 115-16°, VIIIb 87°, VIIIc 65-6°. IR $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ cm^{-1} : 1705 (>C=O stretch). These were converted into the corresponding benzenepropanamides (IX) by conversion to acid chlorides with SOCl_2 followed by treatment with ammonia and were crystallized from benzene-pet. ether as white solids, m.p. IXa 130°, IXb 115-16°, IXc 96-7°. IR $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ cm^{-1} : 350 and 3170 (N-H stretch) and 1665 (>C=O stretch).

IX were reduced with LAH in anhydrous ether and the amines were isolated as hydrochlorides, crystallized from methanol-ethyl acetate as white shinning flaky solids. These were characterised by elemental analysis and spectral data. IR $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ cm^{-1} :

3040-2820 (N-H stretch), 1580 and 1510 (N-H bend). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (TFA) : δ 1.0-1.2 (t, $-\text{CH}_3$), 1.50 (t, $-\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH}_2$ and saturated $-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.2 (s, $\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_3$ and m, $\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{NH}-$), 2.60-2.80 (m, 2 X $\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_2-$), 3.2 (m, $\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{NH}-$), 4.20 (q, $-\text{OCH}_2-$), 6.76 (1H, s, $\text{Ar}-\text{H}$), 7.06 (1H, s, $\text{Ar}-\text{H}$).

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